

*THOUGHTS ON THE SOCIAL
CONTRACT*

by Musa Islam Rahi

Preface

Thoughts on the Social Contract is an essay aimed at understanding and reflecting upon the Social Contract theory by **Jean Jacques Rousseau**. The purpose of this essay is not mere commentary, but rather to preserve the self-discussion and reasoning. At certain points in the essay I switch between the concepts of Jean Jacques Rousseau and mine own without prior warning, and as such I warn you to not read this as to merely understand the theory but to reason at each paragraph as if it were a late night discussion between Rousseau, Musa and you. This is the first essay of a most likely three essay work. This essay covers the Book 1 of the social contract by Jean Jacques Rousseau, the next essay shall cover Book 2, and the last essay shall cover Book 3 & 4 together.

Book I

*Man was born free, and everywhere he is in chain. A person deems himself master of others, yet still remains more of a slave than they. How did this change come about? I do not know. What can make it legitimate? I think I can resolve that question.*¹

Man was born free, yet he is an endless chain of obligations. Any authority among men, what can be its legitimacy? That is precisely what Jean Jacques Rousseau intends to answer, **the legitimacy of authority**. From this question begins a journey exploring the legitimacy of multiple authorities contemporary to Rousseau.

¹ Social Contract by Jean Jacques Rousseau, Book 1, Chapter 1

1. The Authority of Force.

The first and arguably the most ancient authority among men was the authority of force, the authority of might is right. Rousseau calls it the right of the Strongest.

‘Whence (from where) the right of the strongest?’²

Rousseau asks from where does this right of the strongest come, it is nothing more than physical power and as such no morality can result from it, so how can being strong be the legitimacy behind an authority? It cannot be, for being subservient to someone stronger than you is not an act of duty, or morality but an act of necessity, an act of survival. Today, individuals in the sphere of polity of a state claim to be an authority from force, such as dictators, they claim to have a right to rule based on their power (strength) to keep the rule. But Jean Jacques Rousseau raises an interesting point here. If an individual who is stronger than the dictator attempts to overthrow him and succeeds, does the right of the strongest not change from the dictator to that individual who overthrew him? In

² Social Contract by Jean Jacques Rousseau, Book 1, Chapter 3

Rousseau's other terms, cause changes the effect, and such a right is arbitrary because by the same cause (power) you claim the effect (right) can be the cause of effect upon you. By the same right a people is oppressed can be the same right by which a people rebel.

2. Hereditary claim to Power, Domination or to Slavery.

Often the rulers with whom the people are discontented attempt another claim to mislead the masses. The claim of Natural Right, or the hereditary claim to Power, mostly seen in monarchist or feudal leaning states. Rousseau critiques the idea of hereditary, natural claim to power, domination or to slavery, subservient behavior. He goes on to advocate against the idea that human race supposedly belongs to a hundred individuals with rights from nature. He implies the same technique as he does in critique against the right of the strongest – cause and effect. According to Jean an individual's nature is more suited to slavery or to some natural claim to power not because he has some sort of right from the nature but

because of the cause – the cause being that he has been brought up in an environment which he now mirrors, a slave is of the subservient behavior only because he has been brought up or forced into slavery – and when the cause changes the effect changes. When the environment changes the individual changes, thus exposing the non-existent natural right. Such a right is no more and no less illegitimate, arbitrary than the right of the strongest.

3. The First Societies & the Alienation of People as a Whole.

Hugo Grotius³ asks a question, if a man can alienate⁴ himself to a master, why cannot a people as whole do the same? Why cannot the people as a whole give itself to a King? To which Jean Jacques Rousseau responds by highlighting a clear point of contention, but before discussing this point of contention we

³ Hugo Grotius (1583-1645) was a Dutch philosopher and jurist, often called the father of modern international law.

⁴ According to the Social Contract by Jean Jacques Rousseau, Book 1, Chapter 4, to alienate is to give or to sell.

must discuss the First Societies. First societies can be defined as the grundnorm⁵ of all societies. Rousseau describes family as the first and the oldest form of a society.

‘The oldest of all societies and the only natural one is that of the family. Yet children remain bound to the father only so long as they need him in order to survive. No sooner does this need cease than the natural bond is dissolved. If they do continue to remain united, this is no longer natural but voluntary, the family itself is maintained only through convention.’⁶

Rousseau here declares that children are bound to their fathers only as long as they need him to survive and only as long as the children derive their subsistence⁷ from the father. He further says that there is only one difference between a father and his children, and a ruler and his people. A father is repaid by the

⁵ Grundnorm is a term coined by Han Kelsen, in his work the Pure Theory of Law. Grundnorm means the most basic thing, it means the norm from which all other norms are derived, in case of societies it means the first society from which all other societies originate.

⁶ Social Contract by Jean Jacques Rousseau, Book 1, Chapter 2

⁷ Subsistence means the basic means of living or survival, such as food, water, and shelter.

pleasure of love he feels for taking care of his children while a ruler is repaid with the pleasure of power in return for the love he does not have for his people. Now that we have understood the concept of the first society – family – according to Jean Jacques Rousseau, we will move on to the answer which he gave to the question of Hugo Grotius. If a man can alienate himself to a master, why cannot a people as whole do the same? Jean says that a person can only alienate his own liberty, not others, a person can alienate his children's liberties but not irrevocably and without condition for doing such is arbitrary and against the aims of nature. For children only belong to the father as long as they need him to survive. How can a person give up something as a whole which he does not fully own. For example, how can a person sell a house completely while he only owns a part of it?

'Hence, for an arbitrary government to be legitimate, it would be necessary for the people in each generation to have the power to accept or reject

it (power to accept or reject the government).⁸

Only when each generation has such power can the government be declared legitimate.

4. The Alienation of Liberty as an Individual.

‘To renounce your liberty is to renounce your character as a man – the rights and even the duties of humanity. There is no possible compensation for someone who renounces everything. To strip his will of all liberty means to strip his actions of all morality.’⁹

Just as we had to understand the concept of first society before continuing on about alienation of a people as whole, we have to first understand the concept of liberty as Rousseau describes it. The writing of Jean Jacques Rousseau is like debris after an explosion, its spread everywhere, thus the difficulty in understanding him. He describes liberty in a social contract as civil liberty. It is endowing ones actions with morality and to act according to reason, act in a manner consensual with himself. **He describes civil**

⁸ Social Contract by Jean Jacques Rousseau, Book 1, Chapter 4

⁹ Social Contract by Jean Jacques Rousseau, Book 1, Chapter 4

liberty as when a man has morality, consent, and reason in his actions. Now that we have understood the concept of liberty, we can safely assume that Rousseau is a hard liner against the concept of alienation of liberty, so am I, but with respect to his great mind, to me Rousseau here is no more practical than Hugo Grotius was in his reasoning. To renounce your liberty is an action no one is fond of. No one surrenders their liberty willingly (with consent) according to Rousseau, thus making such action as not one of convention, agreement but illegitimate. For the purposes of humanity, and for the purposes of my stance against slavery, alienation of liberty I agree with him, but for the purpose of the practicality of his reasoning I beg to differ. It is as Rousseau says, man is born free but everywhere he is in chains. A person is always in chains to his **hierarchy of objective values**, some certain ideals, which he holds to dearly. For example, each person holds the ideal of life in such a list. The list I speak of can be defined as the levels of personal moral wealth. An example of such hierarchy can be seen in the

table down below,

Most valued	Life
2 nd most valued	Liberty
3 rd most valued	Health
4 th most valued	Wealth

Atop such list sits the dear value of life for most people, and most often liberty comes second. There is no limit to the length of such a list, but the more valued a section is, the clearer the hierarchy is. Moving onwards, in such cases where a person has to give up his liberty, I believe his morality can still exist, unlike Rousseau. A person may surrender his liberty in hopes of later recovering it, and in hopes of preserving the most valued life. **A person may reason and consent with himself to give up morality (liberty) in order to preserve the moral agent, and in doing such an act give birth to an alternative source of morality – the reasoning and the consent with himself.** In cases, where a person does not hold the value of life as the most valued but something else, then the very act of death

(giving up life for the sake of the most valued) becomes an act of morality. Then death becomes love, for only a true lover can do such. To Rousseau, I would like to say that not all can be derived from rigid reasoning alone, for some things are subjective, such as the hierarchy of the objective list is subjective to the distinct nature of each human. The placement of each value is subject to changes by the moral agent but the list in itself remains objective. It is within the sphere of morality of an individual to preserve the most valued, to preserve his life and hope for the restoration his liberty. For the sake of displaying the absurdity of reason alone I can say that all slaves should have committed suicide to make futile the profession of slavery for the masters. Since they did not kill themselves, from this we can conclude they did indeed hold life as the most valued, now whether they hoped to achieve liberty one day or not depends on what their hierarchy was, and indeed also depends upon what their background was.

5. Master/Slaves versus Ruler/People.

To this point Rousseau has established that the right of force, claim of some natural right to power, domination or to slavery, subservient behavior, alienation of people as a whole is illegitimate. Therefore, now he moves towards shaping the legitimate. He begins to do such by differentiating between an illegitimate master/slave relationship and a legitimate Ruler/People relationship.

*'In the fact that dispersed men may have successively have been enslaved – in whatever numbers – to a single individual, I perceive only a master and slaves, and by no means a people and its ruler. It is an aggregation, if you will, but not association; neither public good nor body politic is involved here.'*¹⁰

In doing the differentiation he provides us with his conditions for legitimacy, in order for an authority to be legitimate, it must involve two things, **public good and body politic.**

¹⁰ Social Contract by Jean Jacques Rousseau, Book 1, Chapter 5

6. State of Nature.

The Social Contract theory can be defined as the theory of the passage from the State of Nature to Social Pact and then to a legitimate Civil State. Till now we have understood what the civil state is not, we have yet to understand the Social Pact but first we must understand the concept of the State of Nature. It is not a concept explicitly agreed on by philosophers and as such we will stay true to how Rousseau himself defined it.

State of Nature	Social Contract	Civil State
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Rousseau defines the state of nature as an epoch where man is guided by his instinct, and his actions lack morality, and where the man had only thought of himself. He called such as a state of natural liberty. He further distinguishes between natural liberty and civil liberty.

‘What a man loses through the social contract is his natural liberty, and a limitless right to all that tempts him and that he can reach. What he wins is

*civil liberty.....*¹¹

Now that we have understood that the aim of the social contract is to take men from the state of natural liberty to civil liberty, we must now attempt to understand how the social contract attempts to achieve it.

7. The Pact before the Pact.

Rousseau says that men arrived at a point where it was necessary for their survival, preservation to flock together and ‘engender’ a new united force through aggregation. But the question arises here, is this not the aggregation of necessity of survival instead of being an act of morality, does this not mean such aggregation is now illegitimate by Rousseau’s own definition? The answer is yes, but only if this was indeed the social pact, but it is only the pact before the social pact, it is this pact which led to the moral conditions to form a legitimate social contract, to form a legitimate authority.

‘For if the conflict of particular interests made the establishment of societies necessary, it is the

¹¹ Social Contract by Jean Jacques Rousseau, Book 1, Chapter 8

*agreement of those same interests that made it possible.*¹²

Though this can be interpreted in certain different ways, I tend to do it in a way most beneficial to the legitimacy of the contract. When people with private and different interests aggregated together in order to survive, it led to major conflicts between them, which would have plummeted them back into the danger they wished to escape. These conflicts formed the moral conditions. Thus, the people through reasoning and consent arrived at the common interest to end all the conflicts which led to a legitimate, and moral social contract. Adam Rosenfeld called the pact before the general pact as a whisper of the public good, and body politic.¹³

8. The Social Contract.

Now that the basis of the social contract have been established as legitimate, Rousseau moves on to shaping up the social contract.

¹² Social Contract by Jean Jacques Rousseau, Book 2, Chapter 1

¹³ Lecture on Social Contract, Book 1, 50th minute by Adam Rosenfeld, YouTube

‘How to find a form of association that will, with the whole common force, defend and protect the person and goods of each associate, and through which each individual, while uniting with all, will nevertheless obey only himself alone and remain as free as before?’¹⁴

How to form a social contract in which each person is with liberty, yet part of the whole? Rousseau answer this with a brilliant line of reasoning,

‘...the total alienation of each associate with all his rights to the community as a whole.’¹⁵

Rousseau backs up his solution by stating these reasons,

- I. All alienate themselves completely thus the condition is equal for all,
- II. Since everyone gives themselves to everyone, no one gives themselves to anyone,
- III. Since the condition is equal for all, no one has any benefit in making the condition difficult for the rest.

¹⁴ Social Contract by Jean Jacques Rousseau, Book 1, Chapter 6

¹⁵ Social Contract by Jean Jacques Rousseau, Book 1, Chapter 6

9. General Will.

Now that each person has alienated himself, how shall community as a whole govern itself? The community as a whole shall govern itself through general will, though some of you might not have caught it but we have already defined general will; it is the common good and body politic which was also the condition for legitimacy of an authority according to Rousseau. Thus, the general will can be defined as a legitimate system of governance. Rousseau does not define general will in detail in Book I, but he provides us with its essence, **the will of all for all.**

10. General Will as the Sovereign and the Preservation of Civil Liberty.

Rousseau defines General Will as the supreme authority, as the sole sovereign, and in doing so he engenders the individuals involved in the social contract into two entities that exist at the same time. One entity being the general will, the sovereign composed of the members as a whole and other being the private individuals subject to the sovereign. Since

sovereign is composed of the individuals themselves, Rousseau fulfills the condition of consent he sets for civil liberty to exist. Thus, the transition from natural liberty to civil liberty is accomplished. Body Politic, and Civil Liberty have been accomplished but what of common good? What is the guarantor of common good?

*‘...the sovereign being formed only by the individuals who make it up, neither has nor can have any interest contrary to theirs; hence, the Sovereign power has no need of a guarantor against its subjects....’*¹⁶

Rousseau says that since the condition is equal for all, why would someone wish to harm themselves? Why would people hurt themselves through their own decisions? Common good has been established, but what is the guarantee of the loyalty of individuals to the whole? There is none, an individual may provide nothing to the whole while benefiting from it and Rousseau calls this very act as the destruction of the Social Contract and the return to the state of nature, and in order to

¹⁶ Social Contract by Jean Jacques Rousseau, Book 1, Chapter 7

protect the social contract from such, he forms the concept which is perhaps the most confusing in Book I.

11. Loyalty of the Individuals to the Whole.

Rousseau in attempts to safeguard the guarantee the loyalty of individuals to the whole says,

‘whosoever refuses to obey the general will shall be constrained to do so by the entire body. This means nothing other than that he shall be forced to be free.’¹⁷

How can someone be forced to be free? Aren’t these concepts in themselves contradictory?

No, Rousseau defines liberty not as the freedom of speech as a modern libertarian understands it. But rather he defines liberty, namely civil liberty as the rules one makes for himself, as consent and morality. Thus, when one gives himself to the whole, he gives himself to none since the condition is equal for all. When he is forced by the whole to be free, no one more or less than himself is forcing himself to be free.

¹⁷ Social Contract by Jean Jacques Rousseau, Book 1, Chapter 7

12. Principles Established.

Before concluding of Book I, and beginning our journey through Book II, **we must first lay down the principles established by Jean Jacques Rousseau,**

- I. The Right of the Strongest is an illegitimate right.
- II. The Rights through hereditary or natural claim to power, domination or to slavery is illegitimate.
- III. Giving up liberty is an act with no compensation, and it strips the actions of an individual of all morality.
- IV. A father cannot give up the liberty of his children irrevocably and without condition.
- V. People as a whole cannot alienate themselves legitimately to a King.
- VI. The conditions for legitimate authority are public good and body politic.
- VII. General Will is a legitimate system of governance.
- VIII. Civil Liberty is preserved under a Civil State, and general will.

13. Conclusion.

The change from State of Nature to a Civil State brings about a change in man, in the form of the transition from natural liberty to civil liberty.

‘.....entire soul soars so high that if the abuses of this new condition did not often degrade him below that from which he emerged, he ought continually to bless the happy moment that wrested him thence forever...’¹⁸

This underlines the positive motive of Rousseau’s mostly brilliant attempt. But we have only yet covered one of the four books of Jean Jacques Rousseau, in the next book he deals more explicitly with the general will and the concept of sovereignty in practicality. According to a letter of Rousseau to Marcet de Mezieres – Genevan watchmaker and a friend of Rousseau – the Social Contract can be reduced to just two principles, that the legitimate sovereignty always belongs to the people & that the aristocracy is the best form of the government.¹⁹

¹⁸ Social Contract by Jean Jacques Rousseau, Book 1, Chapter 8

¹⁹ Routledge, Philosophy Guide Book to Rousseau